

Steady-State Analysis of Saturated Type IV Wind Turbines Under Non-Faulty Operations

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Abstract - The back-to-back converter connection of type IV wind turbine generators (WTGs) implies operational behaviors that differ from conventional synchronous generators. One difference is that type IV WTGs have injection limitations based on their converters' capacity. During regular (non-faulty) operations, the WTG may saturate its converter's capacity depending on the grid conditions, making it technically unfeasible for the WTG voltage to achieve the set reference. Such scenarios lead the WTG to new equilibrium points where the converter limitation determines the operation. This paper proposes a power flow approach to capture the described behavior and yield accurate steady-state estimations of saturated WTGs. The method leverages the computational advantages of a rectangular Newton-Raphson formulation for faster convergence. The obtained results indicate that the proposed methodology achieves estimations with errors below 1% in comparison to a field-validated EMT model.

keywords: Wind turbine generators, inverter-based resources, steady-state analysis

1 Introduction

Energy providers such as type IV wind turbine generators (WTGs), battery systems, and photovoltaic sources are electrically decoupled from the grid due to back-to-back converters. For this reason, such inverter-based resources (IBRs) can behave differently from conventional synchronous generators in specific scenarios. For instance [1–6] have analyzed the during-fault operation of grid-following

type IV WTGs, highlighting how these IBRs behave as grid code- and voltage-dependent current sources in such situations.

Another distinction between type IV WTGs and synchronous generators arises during non-faulty operations where the WTG saturates its current injection due to the converter's current capacity (I_M). Depending on the grid conditions, i.e., short circuit ratio (SCR), reactance over resistance ratio (X/R), and grid voltage (V_{sys}), meeting the WTG active power and voltage setpoints requires injecting a current magnitude that exceeds I_M . Therefore, such scenarios lead the WTG to equilibrium points that, despite delivering the reference active power, imply voltage levels greater than the setpoint to enable feasible injections. Adequately capturing such behavior is crucial for studies such as small signal stability assessments. In particular, addressing exclusively the steady state of such phenomena has a computational advantage compared with methods that also retrieve dynamics. The authors do not know of any literature analyzing such saturated operations from a steady-state perspective.

This paper presents a Newton-Raphson power flow expansion to model the behavior described in the previous paragraph. In other words, the goal of this work is to accurately estimate steady state (equilibrium) points related to non-faulty saturated WTGs, being crucial to emphasize that dynamics do not matter for such studies. The classical Newton-Raphson formulation utilizes equations based on power mismatches written in polar form [7]. However, [5, 8–10] have demonstrated the advantages of Current-based Rectangular Newton-Raphson (CRNR) formulations regarding computational memory usage and convergence time.

Beyond this introduction, Section 2 revises CRNR, Section 3 presents the methodology for analyzing the mentioned saturated operations, Section 4 provides results and discussions, and Section 5 concludes the work.

2 Current injection power flow algorithm

Da Costa, Martins, and Pereira [8] proposed CRNR by implementing two aspects differently from the classical approach. First, the calculations are based on current instead of power equations. Second, phasors are in rectangular rather than polar form, meaning that such complex numbers are represented by their active/real and reactive/imaginary components instead of magnitudes and phases. These features yield Jacobian matrices in which most elements are

constant over the iterative process. This implies computational benefits since there are fewer calculations per iteration than the classical method. From its original implementation, CRNR has been enhanced [9, 11, 12] and utilized in distinct applications [5, 13–16].

As a reminder, power flow studies typically represent buses as PQ , PV , or $V\delta$, where P and Q are the active and reactive power, V and δ are the voltage magnitude and phase. The PQ type represents load buses with known active and reactive power demands. The PV type represents generators with known active power and voltage references. The $V\delta$ type usually regards high-capacity generators with a known voltage, serving as a phase reference for the grid and often utilized to model a system equivalent.

For PQ buses, (1) and (2) are the specified active and reactive currents, whereas (3) and (4) calculate currents according to Ohm's law. Mismatches come from (5). In those equations and others across this paper, I represents the current; superscripts s and c indicate specified and calculated quantities; subscripts a and r represent active (real component) and reactive (imaginary component) quantities; subscripts k and i denote system buses; N is the total number of buses in the system representation. Therefore, for example, a variable $I_{r_k}^c$ indicates the calculated reactive current at bus k . Derivatives of I_a^s and I_r^s are null if and only if the PQ bus has no loads.

$$I_{a_k}^s = (P_k^s V_{a_k} + Q_k^s V_{r_k}) / (V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2) \quad (1)$$

$$I_{r_k}^s = (P_k^s V_{r_k} - Q_k^s V_{a_k}) / (V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2) \quad (2)$$

$$I_{a_k}^c = \sum_{i=1}^N (G_{ki} V_{a_i} - B_{ki} V_{r_i}) \quad (3)$$

$$I_{r_k}^c = \sum_{i=1}^N (G_{ki} V_{r_i} + B_{ki} V_{a_i}) \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta I_{r_k} = I_{r_k}^s - I_{r_k}^c, \Delta I_{a_k} = I_{a_k}^s - I_{a_k}^c, \quad (5)$$

where $P_k^s = P_k^g - P_k^l$ and $Q_k^s = Q_k^g - Q_k^l$, with superscripts g and l indicated generation and load, respectively.

In CRNR, PV buses also rely on (5). However, one needs to model Q^g of such buses as variables since they are unknown, implying the need for one additional mismatch equation to form the Jacobian. Such equation comes from the PV bus' voltage magnitude, as in

$$\Delta V_k = V_k^s - V_k^c = 0, V_k^c = \sqrt{V_{a_k}^2 + V_{r_k}^2} \quad (6)$$

which allows V_k^c to change over the iterations while ensuring it converges to the given reference. Note that the algorithm initiates with

$Q_k^g = 0$. Differentiating the PQ and PV mismatches yields a $2(N-1)+nPV$ Jacobian, as in

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \underline{V}_a \\ \Delta \underline{V}_r \\ \Delta \underline{Q}^g \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{J} & \mathcal{X} \\ \mathcal{Z} & \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \underline{I}_r \\ \Delta \underline{I}_a \\ \Delta \underline{V} \end{bmatrix}_h \quad (7)$$

where h indicates the iteration.

$$\mathcal{J} = - \begin{bmatrix} \partial \Delta I_r / \partial \underline{V}_a & \partial \Delta I_r / \partial \underline{V}_r \\ \partial \Delta I_a / \partial \underline{V}_a & \partial \Delta I_a / \partial \underline{V}_r \end{bmatrix}, \mathcal{X} = - \begin{bmatrix} \partial \Delta I_r / \partial \underline{Q}^g \\ \partial \Delta I_a / \partial \underline{Q}^g \end{bmatrix}, \mathcal{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \partial \underline{V}^c / \partial \underline{V}_a \\ \partial \underline{V}^c / \partial \underline{V}_r \end{bmatrix}^T, \quad (8)$$

where \mathcal{J} is a $2(N-1)$ square matrix formed by 2 by 2 blocks. The “minus 1” is due to the slack bus removal. \mathcal{Z} and \mathcal{X} are nPV by $2(N-1)$ and $2(N-1)$ by nPV matrices, respectively, with nPV denoting the number of PV buses in the system. Note that underscored quantities denote vectors. The algorithm then updates the problem variables according to

$$\begin{bmatrix} \underline{V}_a \\ \underline{V}_r \\ \underline{Q}^g \end{bmatrix}_{h+1} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{V}_a \\ \underline{V}_r \\ \underline{Q}^g \end{bmatrix}_h + \begin{bmatrix} \Delta \underline{V}_a \\ \Delta \underline{V}_r \\ \Delta \underline{Q}^g \end{bmatrix}_h. \quad (9)$$

Fig. 1 illustrates a CRNR Jacobian related to the IEEE 14 bus system, which comprises 9 PQ and 4 PV buses.

FIGURE 1. CRNR Jacobian – IEEE 14 bus system. \mathcal{J} 's constant blocks in blue, \mathcal{J} 's updated blocks in red, \mathcal{X} in green, and \mathcal{Z} in black.

Off-diagonal blocks of \mathcal{J} depend only on the constant elements of the admittance matrix (Y), dismissing recalculations during the iterations. Diagonal blocks of unloaded PQ buses are also constant. Matrix \mathcal{Z} is formed by differentiating (6) regarding the problem variables, whereas \mathcal{X} comes from taking derivatives of all mismatches regarding the Q^g variables.

Readers interested in details about derivative calculations to obtain the CRNR Jacobian are referred to [8, 12]. The following section discusses the CRNR enhancement to address the steady-state operation of saturated type IV WTGs.

3 Methodology

As mentioned in Section 1, certain grid conditions can lead a type IV WTG to saturate its converter's capacity. In such scenarios, the WTG converges to an equilibrium point where the voltage level differs from the given reference, which enables a feasible operation regarding I_M .

During non-saturated operations, the WTG behaves as a *PV* bus, meaning it follows active power and voltage references as a conventional generator. An algorithm such as CRNR is fully capable of capturing the WTG's behavior and estimating non-faulty steady states. However, when saturation occurs, the WTG no longer behaves as a *PV* bus due to the non-feasibility of achieving the voltage reference. In contrast, the WTG maintains the active power reference while injecting the maximum feasible current magnitude, i.e., I_M . Such aspects classify a *PI* bus type, i.e., a scenario where the bus follows specifications for active power and current magnitude. Such a type does not exist in classical power flow approaches and emerges with the ever-growing penetration of IBRs in electrical power systems.

Analogously to *PQ* and *PV* buses, one needs to obtain the V_a and V_r of a *PI* bus, thus requiring two mismatch equations. This paper addresses this task by writing active power and current magnitude equations. In rectangular form, the calculated active power for bus k is obtained through

$$P_k^c = V_{a_k} I_{a_k}^c + V_{r_k} I_{r_k}^c, \quad (10)$$

where $I_{r_k}^c$ and $I_{a_k}^c$ come from (3) and (4), respectively. The calculated current magnitude for bus k is yielded by

$$I_k^c = \sqrt{(I_{a_k}^c)^2 + (I_{r_k}^c)^2}. \quad (11)$$

The mismatch equations are given by

$$\Delta P = P_k^s - P_k^c, \Delta I = I_k^s - I_k^c, \quad (12)$$

where P_k^s is the active power setpoint and $I_k^s = I_M$, i.e., the converter's maximum current magnitude.

Assembling the Jacobian matrix requires retrieving the derivatives of the mismatches with respect to the problem variables. Since P_k^s and I_k^s are constants, such derivatives depend solely on the calculated quantities, as in

$$\frac{\partial P_k^c}{\partial V_{a_k}} = G_{kk}V_{a_k} + B_{kk}V_{r_k} + I_{a_k}^c \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial P_k^c}{\partial V_{r_k}} = G_{kk}V_{r_k} - B_{kk}V_{a_k} + I_{r_k}^c \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial P_k^c}{\partial V_{a_i}} = G_{ki}V_{a_k} + B_{ki}V_{r_k}, i \neq k \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial P_k^c}{\partial V_{r_i}} = G_{ki}V_{r_k} - B_{ki}V_{a_k}, i \neq k \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial I_k^c}{\partial V_{a_k}} = \frac{G_{kk}I_{a_k}^c + B_{kk}I_{r_k}^c}{\sqrt{(I_{a_k}^c)^2 + (I_{r_k}^c)^2}} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\partial I_k^c}{\partial V_{r_k}} = \frac{G_{kk}I_{r_k}^c - B_{kk}I_{a_k}^c}{\sqrt{(I_{a_k}^c)^2 + (I_{r_k}^c)^2}} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial I_k^c}{\partial V_{a_i}} = \frac{G_{ki}I_{a_k}^c + B_{ki}I_{r_k}^c}{\sqrt{(I_{a_k}^c)^2 + (I_{r_k}^c)^2}}, i \neq k \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial I_k^c}{\partial V_{r_i}} = \frac{G_{ki}I_{r_k}^c - B_{ki}I_{a_k}^c}{\sqrt{(I_{a_k}^c)^2 + (I_{r_k}^c)^2}}, i \neq k, \quad (20)$$

where G and B are the real and imaginary parts of \dot{Y} ; double subscripts indicate the row and column within a matrix.

The Newton-Raphson formulation in (7) expands to

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta V_a \\ \Delta V_r \\ \Delta Q^g \end{bmatrix}_h = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{J} & \mathcal{X} \\ \mathcal{J}' \\ \mathcal{Z} \end{bmatrix}_h^{-1} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \Delta I_r \\ \Delta I_a \\ \Delta P \\ \Delta I \\ \Delta V \end{bmatrix}_h \quad (21)$$

$$\mathcal{J}' = \begin{bmatrix} \partial P^c / \partial V_a & \partial P^c / \partial V_r \\ \partial I^c / \partial V_a & \partial I^c / \partial V_r \end{bmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

hence enabling the inclusion of saturated WTGs behaving as PI buses in the CRNR algorithm. Observe that the new ΔP and ΔI mismatches do not depend on the Q_g variables. Therefore, matrix \mathcal{X} is unaffected.

During the iterative process, the WTG can switch between the *PV* and *PI* types. At the end of every iteration, if the WTG is a *PV* bus and the current injection has a magnitude greater than I_M , it changes to *PI*. In contrast, if the WTG is a *PI* bus and its voltage magnitude is less than or equal to the reference, its type changes to *PV*.

It is fundamental to note that such behaviors as *PV* or *PI* buses only apply to steady-state studies, thus relating to this paper's investigation. Such simplified models cannot capture dynamic changes, which are outside the scope of this work.

The following section explores saturation scenarios and demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed CRNR expansion in addressing the steady-state operation of saturated WTGs.

4 Results and discussions

This work investigates a type IV WTG connected to a Thevenin equivalent system, as illustrated in Fig. 2. Z_{fi} and Z_{bt} are the WTG's filter and joint busbar-transformer impedances. Although these cannot be disclosed due to intellectual property, replicating this paper's method can be achieved by neglecting Z_{fi} and taking Z_{bt} as $j0.1$, which causes deviations of less than 3% in results. The WTG behaves either as a *PV* or as a *PI* bus, according to the grid conditions and WTG references. Based on *SCR* and *X/R* inputs, the system's equivalent impedance (Z_{th}) comes from

$$Z_{th} = SCR^{-1} \quad (23)$$

$$R_{th} = Z_{th} / \sqrt{1 + (X/R)^2}, X_{th} = \sqrt{Z_{th}^2 - R_{th}^2}. \quad (24)$$

FIGURE 2. Single bus equivalent system.

Before accounting for the saturated behavior, steady-state estimations disregarded I_M and considered distinct *SCR* and *X/R* values to demonstrate saturation. Figs. 3 to 6 indicate, in red, which combinations of parameters led to current injections that exceed I_M , with feasible injections depicted in blue.

FIGURE 3. Operation scenarios, $SCR = 3$ and $X/R=2$.

FIGURE 4. Operation scenarios, $SCR = 10$ and $X/R=2$.

FIGURE 5. Operation scenarios, $SCR = 3$ and $X/R=10$.

FIGURE 6. Operation scenarios, $SCR = 10$ and $X/R=10$.

When saturation occurs, the WTG cannot meet the voltage reference and ultimately converges to a new equilibrium point. Figs. 3 to 6 suggest that saturation correlates more with variations in SCR than in X/R . However, the main message is that the converter can saturate in several grid scenarios.

The simulations ahead consider the possible saturated behavior of WTGs. Results are compared against an industrial EMT (electromagnetic transients) PSCADTM model representing the type IV WTG. In the EMT simulations, aerodynamic and shaft models define the mechanical system. The electrical part includes the permanent magnet synchronous generator, back-to-back converter, DC link, grid-side converter reactor, filter, WTG transformer with saturation and frequency-dependent impedance, and measurement ports. The control system encompasses the WTG level controller with reduced-order characteristics required for EMT simulations. In addition, it includes the actual grid-following converter controller and the DC link. The model contains the full-order real converter control and protection codes embedded as a *.dll* file. The steady-state analytical codes were

implemented in Matlab, version R2022a, and executed in a 64 GB RAM, Intel® Core™ i9-11950H 2.6 GHz workstation.

It is highlighted that the utilized EMT model developed in PSCAD has been validated against a field turbine, thus enabling a high-quality benchmark for the implemented steady-state approach.

Table 1 provides the input parameters for nine different cases that cause the WTG to saturate its converter's capacity. Note that $I_M = 1.11$ p.u. In all cases, the CRNR algorithm with the extension presented in Section 3 addressed the steady-state behavior of the WTG to estimate the new equilibrium points. Fig. 7 plots the estimations with the EMT results.

TABLE 1. Input parameters for EMT simulations and steady-state analytical estimations, with V_{sys} , V^s , and P^s in p.u.

Case	SCR	X/R	V_{sys}	V^s	P^s
1	1.75	2.00	1.15	0.85	1
2	8.00	20.00	1.00	0.85	1
3	8.00	20.00	1.15	0.85	1
4	8.00	20.00	1.15	0.85	0.54
5	8.00	2.00	1.00	0.85	1
6	8.00	2.00	1.15	0.85	1
7	8.00	2.00	1.15	0.85	0.54
8	8.00	2.00	1.15	0.85	0.11
9	8.00	2.00	1.15	1.00	1.09

FIGURE 7. CRNR estimations against EMT results

Fig. 7 reveals suitable matches between the analytical estimations and the EMT simulations. Across all cases, the mean absolute error is equal to 0.83 ± 0.26 %, with a maximum error of 1.20 %. Such results suggest that the proposed approach based on the novel PI type from Section 3 can adequately capture the behavior of type IV WTGs that experience saturation due to the converter's injection limit.

The method in this paper can be a valuable tool to aid small-signal stability studies, which require equilibrium points to conduct assessments. The main advantage of such an analytical approach is the simulation time. For the setup utilized in this work, the steady-state estimations took, on average, five milliseconds to converge.

5 Conclusions

This paper extended the CRNR power flow algorithm to estimate steady-state behaviors of non-faulty type IV WTGs. The work demonstrated scenarios that lead to converter saturation, which standard analytical approaches fail to represent. Results and comparisons against a field-validated EMT model indicate that the described *PI* behavior is suitable to model non-faulty saturated type IV WTGs. In future work, the authors intend to combine this paper's Newton-Raphson implementation with fault-ride-through methods to develop a more general tool for steady-state assessments of type IV WTGs.

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